

FROM FEAR TO COMFORT: ADVANCES IN NEEDLE-FREE INJECTION TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Needle-free injection (NFI) technology is an advanced drug delivery system that eliminates the need for traditional needles. Instead, it uses a high-speed jet of liquid or powder to penetrate the skin and deliver medication into intradermal, subcutaneous, or intramuscular tissues. This approach helps overcome challenges associated with conventional syringes, such as pain, fear of needles, accidental injuries, and risks of infection from reuse. NFI systems are valuable in many fields, including large-scale vaccination, insulin delivery for diabetes, dermatology, and hormone therapy. They are also being explored for biologics, gene therapies, and other sensitive drugs. Several devices, such as Biojector, Vitajet, Intraject, and Madajet, are already available and have shown positive outcomes in clinical use. Different mechanisms spring-powered, gas-propelled, laser-based, and shock-wave systems make these devices versatile for various medical needs. Their main benefits include reduced pain, improved patient comfort, faster administration,

and elimination of needle-related hazards. However, challenges remain, including higher device costs, limited drug compatibility, and the need for training. Ongoing research is focused on improving precision, safety, and affordability. With growing demand for painless

and safe alternatives, needle-free systems are expected to play a major role in future healthcare by enhancing patient compliance, supporting mass immunization, and expanding applications across multiple therapeutic areas.

KEYWORDS: Needle-free injection, jet injector, drug delivery, Clinical trials vaccination, insulin therapy, patient compliance, biologics, marketed products, needle phobia.

INTRODUCTION

Needle-free injections deliver drugs through the skin using high-velocity streams generated by mechanical, pneumatic, or electromagnetic forces. Depending on the design, these systems can target subcutaneous, intradermal, or intramuscular tissues, offering versatility for different therapeutic needs. The mechanism eliminates the need for a physical needle, thereby enhancing patient comfort and safety.

The application of NFI is not limited to improving patient compliance but also extends to public health advantages. In mass vaccination programs, needle-free devices allow rapid administration and reduce risks of cross-infection. They are particularly beneficial for patients requiring frequent injections, such as diabetics on insulin therapy. Furthermore, advancements in biotechnology and formulation science are enabling the use of NFI systems for the delivery of biologics, hormones, and even gene therapies. Despite these advantages, challenges such as high manufacturing costs, the need for precise device calibration, and limitations in drug formulations suitable for high-pressure delivery still exist. Nevertheless, ongoing research and technological innovations continue to address these barriers, making needle-free systems an increasingly viable alternative to conventional injections. (Ravi, Sadhna, Nagpaal, & Chawla, 2015 oct- dec).

Needle-free systems help give medicines without using a traditional needle. They include sprays, edible products, inhalers, and skin patches. Although regular needles are old, needle-free systems are more recent and are being improved. They aim to make giving medicine easier and less painful.

People get injections to protect themselves from diseases like the flu, tetanus, cholera, and typhoid. When a needle goes into the skin, it delivers medicine or a vaccine that helps the body build protection (immunity). But using regular needles has problems.

- They can be expensive.

- They aren't reusable (if reused without sterilizing, they can spread diseases).
- Many people are afraid of needles, so they avoid getting injections.

Because of these problems, scientists have created needle-free ways to give medicines. Needle-free systems are safer, cheaper, easier to use. They can help more people get vaccinated and may reduce the need for antibiotics. They also reduce the risk of healthcare workers accidentally getting pricked by needles, which can be dangerous. (needle-free drug devices), (Al-kaf A. G.)

Now, many companies are working on needle-free options. These include

- Nasal sprays
- Nose drops
- Skin patches
- Air-powered devices
- Even vegetables that contain vaccines

Needle free injection systems are innovative ways to introduce a variety of medicines in patients without piercing the skin. These systems work by the mechanism in which liquid medication is forced at an elevated speed through a small orifice that is held against the skin. Due to this an ultrafine stream of high pressure fluid is created, that penetrates the skin devoid of the use of a needle, thus faster administration of drug occurs as compared to conventional needles.

Needle-free injection (NFI) technology is increasingly being used in clinical trials as a less painful and more convenient alternative to traditional needle injections. These trials often focus on comparing the efficacy and safety of NFI with standard needle injections, particularly for vaccines and other injectable medications. (sd.khalilullah)

- **Advantages and Disadvantages of Needle-Free Injections.**

Advantages	Disadvantages
1. Eliminates the risk of broken needles.	1. Requires a higher initial investment.
2. Ensures consistent and reliable vaccine delivery.	2. Greater complexity.
3. Eliminates the need for needle disposal.	3. Higher training and maintenance requirements.
4. Removes the risk of needle stick injuries for healthcare workers.	4. Lacks a universal "one size fits all" design.
5. Reduces pain and patient stress	5. May face initial lack of confidence from workers.

Key Aspects of Needle-Free Injection in Clinical Trials

- **Pain Reduction and Patient Preference:** A primary driver for using needle-free injectors is to reduce pain and anxiety associated with injections, especially for individuals with needle phobia.
- **Improved Adherence:** By making injections less daunting, needle-free methods may improve patient adherence to prescribed regimens, particularly for chronic conditions requiring regular injections like insulin therapy.
- **Enhanced Immunogenicity:** Some studies suggest that needle-free delivery can lead to a stronger immune response to vaccines, potentially due to more efficient delivery of the vaccine into the skin's immune cells.
- **Bioequivalence and Safety:** Clinical trials aim to demonstrate that needle-free injections are bioequivalent to traditional injections, meaning they deliver the same amount of medication and achieve the same therapeutic effect. Safety profiles are also closely monitored for any differences between the two methods.
- **Specific Applications:** Needle-free injections are being explored in various clinical trial settings, including:
 - **Vaccination:** Evaluating the effectiveness of needle-free delivery for vaccines like influenza, tetanus, and COVID-19.
 - **Insulin Delivery:** Assessing the impact of needle-free insulin injectors on blood glucose control and patient satisfaction.
 - **Other Medications:** Investigating the use of needle-free technology for medications like corticosteroids and local anaesthetics. (Vishwanathaiah S, 2024), (Sonoda)

HISTORY: (Canter J, 1923-1927), (Lockhart, 1940), (needle free injection)

Needle-free injection technology has a history dating back to the late 19th century, with modern devices emerging in the 1930s and 1940s. The technology uses a high-pressure jet to create a fine stream of fluid or powder, delivering medication through the skin without a hollow needle.

19th century: Early ideas of non-needle injection were documented

1866: Dr. Jean Sales - Girons presented the Appareil pour l'aquapuncture to the Imperial Academy of Medicine in Paris. This is the first recorded jet injector designed to administer water or medicine under pressure to penetrate the skin.

Late 1800s: Accidental jet injections from high-pressure grease guns began inspiring the medical community to adapt the technology for drug delivery.

Early-to-mid 20th century: The concept of jet injection was formally patented and developed.

1936: Engineer Marshall Lockhart filed a patent for a jet injection system, paving the way for modern devices.

1940s: "High-pressure guns" were developed to pierce the skin with a fine stream of liquid, driven by springs or compressed gas. These early, often reusable, devices were widely adopted for mass vaccination programs.

Late 20th century: Safety concerns led to the development of single-use components

1986: A hepatitis B outbreak was linked to a multi-use nozzle jet injector, revealing a risk of cross-contamination from back-splashing fluids.

1997: The U.S. Department of Defence, a major user of jet injectors, stopped using them for mass vaccinations.

1990s: The industry shifted toward disposable cartridge jet injectors (DCJIs). In these systems, the drug reservoir and nozzle are combined into a single-use component to eliminate cross-contamination.

21st century: Research has continued to refine the technology and expand its applications.

2010s: Laser-based and shockwave-based microjet injectors have been developed to achieve even finer control and reduced patient discomfort.

2020s: Modern needle-free systems can handle a wider range of medications, including delicate biological molecules, and are used for applications beyond traditional vaccines and insulin.

Why needle-free injections are better than hypodermic injections?

Hypodermic Injection	Needle-Free Injection(NFI)
1. Cause pain from the needle or the medicine after injection.	1. Less pain at the injection site.
2. Many people have needle fear.	2. Removes fear of needles.
3. Risk of needle breaking or causing tissue injury.	3. Avoids tissue damage as no needle is used.
4. Requires proper training to use.	4. Easy to use, self-injection possible.
5. Can spread infections through needle use.	5. Lower infection risk since no needle used.

6. Hard to insert needle to the right depth.	6. No issue of depth - injection is controlled automatically.
7. Need to check (aspirate) to avoid hitting blood vessels.	7. No need to check – no needle involvement.
8. Risk of spreading diseases by reusing needles.	8. No risk of diseases spread because needles aren't used.

OBJECTIVES

1. To compare traditional needle-based systems with needle-free injection systems.
2. To describe the different types of needle-free injection technologies.
3. To highlight that needle-free injections are less painful and reduce fear among patients.
4. To explain the safety benefits of needle-free systems, such as preventing needle-stick injuries.
5. To emphasize advantages like consistent vaccine/drug delivery and elimination of broken needles.
6. To examine how needle-free systems improve patient comfort and healthcare worker safety.
7. To evaluate the overall role of needle-free injection technology in advancing modern drug delivery.

CLASSIFICATIONS AND MODE OF ACTION OF NEEDLE FREE INJECTION

Based on working principle**= 1. Spring System**

In this system, a spring is used to store energy. When the spring is released, the stored energy is used to push the drug through the skin in the form of a fine jet. It is one of the simplest and cheapest methods.

Problem: As the spring stretches, the force decreases gradually (because of Hooke's law). So, the drug may not be delivered at a constant pressure, which can affect the accuracy of the dose. Example use: Suitable for simple injections where a small amount of drug needs to be delivered.

= 2. Laser Powered System

This system uses a special laser (erbium-doped yttrium garnet laser) to generate energy. The laser heats a tiny amount of water inside the device. The expanding water pushes the medicine forward through a very thin nozzle, creating a microscopic high-speed jet.

The system has

1. A drug holder (adapter) to keep the medicine.
2. A water chamber separated by a membrane. The expanding water drives the drug forward.

Advantage: 1) Very precise control of drug deliver
2) Used in skin treatments and delicate procedures.

= 3. Energy Propelled System

Here, different forms of stored energy (like mechanical, electrical, or thermal) are used to push the drug into the skin. The idea is that any strong and controlled energy source can replace a needle by creating enough pressure to drive medicine inside.

Example: Systems using battery power or electromagnetic energy.

= 4. Lorentz Force System

Based on magnetic fields and electric current.

Main parts: A magnet surrounded by a wire coil.

A piston connected to the drug container (ampoule)

When current is passed through the coil, it creates a magnetic field. This magnetic field pushes the piston forward. The piston forces the drug out as a thin, high-speed stream.

Advantage: Delivers a very fine and controlled jet of medicine. Best use: For eye (corneal) treatments and in paediatrics where delicate dosing is needed.

□ 5. Gas Propelled / Air Forced System (Jet Injectors)

Works by using compressed gas (like nitrogen, carbon dioxide, or helium) to push the drug out. Produces a strong, high-pressure jet that can penetrate the skin. Widely used in mass vaccination programs because it can deliver medicine quickly to many people.

Drawbacks

1. Needs careful safety testing.
2. Sometimes causes bad odour due to combustion gases.
3. Equipment is more complex compared to spring systems.

= 6. Shock Wave System

Uses sudden release of energy to create shock waves. These shock waves move at supersonic speed, producing very high pressure and temperature for a very short time. This pressure is used to drive the medicine through the skin into the body.

Advantage

1. Very powerful and effective.
2. Can deliver drugs without damaging the deeper skin tissues.

Example: Used for targeting specific areas where very high penetration force is required. (Al-kaf A.), (— Geetha Pushpanjali S.)

Based on Type of Load

SYSTEM TYPE 1: POWDER INJECTION

= Design of Powder Injection Systems

- These systems are made with a small chamber that stores the solid drug in powder form.
- A nozzle is attached to release the drug.
- The chamber is powered by compressed gas (like helium or CO₂), which pushes the drug out.
- The chamber is sealed on both sides with a thin diaphragm (just a few microns thick) to keep the drug safe until use.

= Mechanism of Powder Injection

1. Expulsion of particles – When activated, the drug particles are pushed out of the nozzle along with a fast-moving gas stream.
2. Skin penetration – The high-speed particles hit the skin, creating a very tiny opening that becomes deeper as more particles enter.
3. Deposition – The drug particles settle in a round, clustered pattern at the bottom of the opening, crossing the stratum corneum (outer skin layer).
4. Spread inside the skin – After crossing the outer barrier, the particles move further into the viable epidermis (inner skin layer where cells are active).

= Working Principle (Light Gas Gun)

- A light gas gun is used to speed up the particles.
- Inside, a piston rapidly moves forward and accelerates the particles.
- Before hitting the skin, a deceleration mechanism slows down the piston (to avoid damage).
- At this moment, the particles are released at the right velocity to penetrate the tissue safely and effectively.

SYSTEM TYPE 2: LIQUID INJECTION

- The main idea of this system is: when liquid is pushed with enough pressure against the skin, it can pierce through and reach the tissue underneath. This principle is similar to powder injection, but the design and working method are different.

The device usually contains

- Liquid A power source (like compressed gas or a spring) to generate pressure.
- A drug chamber that holds the liquid medicine. A nozzle through which the drug is released.
- The nozzle opening (called an orifice) is usually 150–300 micrometers wide, which is fine enough to create a narrow, high-pressure

Mechanism of Liquid Injections

A piston pushes the liquid inside the nozzle, creating very high pressure and forcing the liquid jet out at a speed of more than 100 m/s. When this fast jet hits the skin, it makes a tiny hole by breaking or eroding the skin surface. As the jet keeps hitting, the hole becomes deeper. If the jet is faster than the hole can form, some liquid may bounce back (splash). Once the hole is deep enough, the jet slows down and liquid starts to collect inside. This stops the hole from getting any deeper. Within a few microseconds, the final size of the hole is fixed. At the bottom of the hole, the liquid spreads inside the skin in a round, ball-like (spherical) shape.

SYSTEM TYPE 3: DEPOT OR PROJECTILE INJECTIONS

These systems are used to give medicine directly into the muscles. When the drug is injected, it forms a small “store” or “depot” inside the muscle tissue. This depot acts like a drug reservoir, which means the medicine stays there for some time instead of mixing quickly into the blood. From this depot, the drug is slowly and steadily released into the body. Because of this slow release, the medicine works for a longer duration without needing frequent injections. This method is often used for medicines like hormones, vaccines, or long-acting pain relievers, where continuous action over days or weeks is required. (Authors: T. R. Kale, 2014), (Mitragotri, 2006)

Based on mechanism of drug delivery**1. Nano patches**

These patches have very tiny projections (not visible to the naked eye). They use an applicator to push the drug through the skin. The drug or vaccine reaches immune cells just under the skin. The process is painless and efficient.

2. Sandpaper-assisted delivery

A sandpaper-like tool is gently rubbed on the skin. This causes micro-derma abrasion (removal of the very thin top skin layer). This increases skin permeability (allows drugs to pass easily). Useful for delivering drugs like Lidocaine and 5-fluorouracil, and also for vaccines. Already common in cosmetic treatments.

3. Iontophoresis -enabled delivery

Normally, the skin blocks salts and charged drug molecules. In this method, a small electric current (~ 0.5 mA/cm²) is applied. Two electrodes (patches) are used: One holds the drug (positively or negatively charged). The other completes the circuit at another body site. The current pushes drug molecules across the skin into the body.

4. Micro-needle patches

These patches have thousands of tiny spikes (~ 750 μ m long). They pierce only the upper skin layer (not deep enough to touch blood vessels or pain nerves). This means no pain but effective drug delivery. Greatly improves patient comfort and compliance. (Saman Zafar, 2025), (Rashmi Hulimane Shivaswamy, 2024), (Sipho Mdanda, 2021).

Based on site of delivery

Intradermal: Used for DNA-based vaccines, this method delivers the substance into the layers of the skin.

Intramuscular: This is the deepest delivery method, commonly used for vaccines.

Subcutaneous: This method delivers medication, such as therapeutic proteins like growth hormones, into the fatty layer just under the skin. (Jarvi, 2021 feb), (Chung-I Rai, 2024 feb)

COMPONENTS OF NEEDLE – FREE INJECTION

INJECTION DEVICE

NOZZLE

PRESSURE SOURCE

Here is a diagram of the components of a needle-free injection device:

Needle-free injection systems are specially designed devices that deliver drugs into the body without using traditional needles. They mainly consist of three important components:

1. Injection Device

This is the main unit of the system and works as a container for the drug. It usually has a drug chamber where the medicine is kept until it is injected. The device is made from plastic materials, which makes it light, safe, and sterile. It is designed in such a way that patients can self-administer the injection easily. Inside the device, there is a special syringe-like system, but it does not use a needle. Instead, it uses pressure to push the medicine through the skin.

2. Nozzle

The nozzle is the pathway through which the drug is delivered into the skin. It is the only part of the device that directly touches the skin. The nozzle contains a very tiny opening (orifice). This opening is usually about 100 Micrometers wide (0.1 mm), which is thinner than a human hair. When the device is activated, the drug is forced out at very high speed (around 100 meters/second), allowing it to penetrate the skin to a depth of about 2 mm. A typical

nozzle opening is about 0.127 mm, which gives an effect similar to a 25-gauge needle but without actually using one

3. Pressure Source

For the drug to enter the body without a needle, strong pressure is needed to push it through the skin barrier.

There are two main ways to create this pressure

➤ Mechanical Pressure

A spring stores energy, and when the plunger is pressed, the energy is released. This sudden release pushes the drug through the nozzle into the skin.

➤ Compressed Gas Pressure

Special gases like carbon dioxide (CO₂) or nitrogen (N₂) are stored in a small cartridge. When released, the gas generates enough force to drive the drug into the skin.

The system is carefully designed to make sure the pressure is strong enough to puncture the skin but at the same time gentle enough to protect the drug molecules so that they are not damaged. (Momin, 2016), (Indrajeet B. Pawar, 2019), (Othman, 2017).

MECHANISM

Needle-free injection technology works by forcing liquid medication at high speed through a tiny orifice that is held against the skin. The diameter of the orifice is smaller than the diameter of a human hair. This creates an ultra-fine stream of high-pressure fluid that penetrates the skin without using a needle.

The mechanism utilizes compressed gas, such as carbon dioxide or nitrogen, to drive the drug through the orifice at extremely high speed. During administration, an ultra-fine fluid stream penetrates the skin layers, rapidly delivering the drug into the systemic circulation. The entire injection process takes less than one-third of a second and occurs in three distinct stages:

Peak Pressure Phase: The phase where optimal pressure is applied to penetrate the skin, lasting less than 0.025 seconds.

Dispersion Phase: The phase in which the drug disperses, lasting approximately 0.2sec.

Drop-Off Phase: The final phase, where pressure reduces, lasting less than 0.05 seconds. (Hye Sung Han, 2021)

Needle-Free Injection Devices

1. Non-prefilled devices (empty devices that are filled before use): These devices must have a long shelf life, usually 2–3 years. The power source (like gas, spring, or mechanical trigger) should stay stable and reliable for years. The device must still work properly even if stored in different environmental conditions (like heat, cold, or humidity)

2. Prefilled devices (already filled with the drug)

Since the drug is stored inside the device, extra care is needed: **Sterility:** The drug must stay completely germ-free until the end of its shelf life. **Safety from toxins and particles:** Any harmful substances (endotoxins, dust, or other small particles) must remain below safe limits. **Material compatibility:** The parts of the device touching the drug should not release harmful chemicals into it. **Drug stability:** The drug must not change in purity, strength, or concentration throughout storage.

Device material

The body of the injector should be:

Chemically inert (not reacting with the drug),

Strong and durable (to handle pressure during injection),

Cost-effective,

Stable in different conditions.

Viscosity and Injection

New medicines often contain larger molecules and need to be concentrated so that a comfortable amount can be injected. In a traditional needle and syringe, the needle acts like a

narrow pipe. This reduces the pressure along its length, making it harder to push thicker (more viscous) fluids. So, when injecting a thick solution, the person must press the plunger much harder than with a thin (less viscous) one. The thicker the fluid, the more force is needed. Needle-free devices avoid this problem. Since they don't use a needle, they can easily deliver medicines of different thicknesses efficiently and without extra effort. (Hye Sung Han, 2021).

MANUFACTURING OF NEEDLE-FREE INJECTION TECHNOLOGY

The manufacturing of needle-free injection (NFI) technology primarily involves the fabrication of device components using injection molding, followed by assembly, labelling, and packaging under sterile conditions. The specific processes vary depending on the type of NFI system, which can be powered by compressed gas, springs, or other energy sources.

Raw material

Since needle-free injection devices come into direct contact with the skin, they must be made from pharmacologically inert materials. Polycarbonates and other synthetic thermoplastics are ideal for the device's outer body because they are lightweight, easy to mold, and durable. Colorants may be added if needed. Gas-powered systems typically use helium or CO₂ for propulsion, and some modern designs even use butane. The device's body must be made of materials that do not react with the gas or any additives, including colorants. Raw materials are processed step by step to create the final product. Individual parts are usually manufactured off-site and then assembled under sterile conditions to ensure safety and hygiene.

Making the Pieces

A common method used in the plastic industry to make devices is called injection molding. In this process, plastic pellets are fed into a machine through a hopper, either by hand or automatically. The hopper moves the pellets into a cylindrical chamber where a rotating screw pushes them forward. As the pellets move, friction and sometimes external heating melt them, turning them into a smooth, flowable plastic. The melted plastic is then injected into a mold under pressure. It is left there to cool and harden into the desired shape. Once solidified, the mold is opened, and the finished piece is removed. Each piece is checked carefully to make sure it has no defects, and then the process starts again.

Assembling and Labelling

The finished pieces are moved to an assembly line, where precise machines add markings, such as dose levels, on the device or its parts. During this stage, workers assemble the different compartments to complete the device. Any additional attachments, like buttons or other components, are also fitted at this point.

Packaging

Once the device is fully assembled and all attachments are in place, it moves to the packaging stage. The device is first wrapped in sterile film and then placed into cardboard or plastic boxes. Any necessary manuals or inserts are included in the boxes. Finally, the boxes are stacked on pallets and prepared for shipment.

Quality Control

Throughout the manufacturing process, products are closely inspected for any visual defects or structural damage. Inspectors also check that all equipment is accurate and precise, and that the product's dimensions and thickness are correct. The final labels and calibration are also verified. Since these devices can have safety issues, they are made under the strict supervision of the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). The FDA regularly inspects the manufacturing facilities to ensure everything is up to standard. (Tosif Khan), (Al-Kaf A.).

ADVANCES IN NEEDLE-FREE INJECTION TECHNOLOGY

Advances in needle free injection technology

Bio-jector 2000

The Bio-jector 2000 is a special type of needle-free injection system that delivers medicines directly into the muscles without using traditional needles. It is the only intramuscular jet injection device approved by the U.S. FDA, which shows its high safety and reliability standards. To prevent the spread of infections between patients, the Bio-jector 2000 uses disposable, single-use syringes. This means every patient gets a fresh syringe, removing the risk of cross-contamination. The system has been used for more than 10 million injections worldwide, and during this time, no major side effects or serious problems have been reported. This proves it is both safe and effective.

The Bio-jector 2000 is particularly valuable in high-risk medical situations, such as when giving injections to patients with HIV or hepatitis, where safety and infection control are very important. Its design ensures that healthcare workers and patients are well-protected. In short, the Bio-jector 2000 is a trusted, needle-free injection system that provides safe, effective, and infection-free delivery of medicines, especially in sensitive or high-risk conditions.

Serojet

The Serojet device is a type of needle-free injection system that was developed as a variation of the earlier Vitajet technology. While Vitajet could be used for different medicines, Serojet was designed specifically for one drug called Serostim. Serostim is a recombinant human growth hormone (rhGH). It is used in the treatment of HIV-associated wasting, a serious condition where patients with HIV lose a lot of weight and muscle mass, often leading to weakness and poor health. By providing growth hormone, Serostim helps patients regain lean body mass, improve strength, and enhance quality of life.

The Serojet device delivers Serostim subcutaneously, meaning the medicine is injected just under the skin instead of deep into the muscles. Because it is needle-free, it reduces pain, needle anxiety, and the risk of accidental needle-stick injuries. In March 2001, the U.S. FDA officially approved the Serojet device for marketing, confirming that it met safety and effectiveness standards. Since then, it has provided patients with a safer and more comfortable alternative for receiving their growth hormone the.

Cool click

The Cool Click system, developed by Bioject, is a needle-free injection device designed especially for children who need Saizen (a recombinant form of human growth hormone).

Some children either do not produce growth hormone naturally or their bodies make it in insufficient amounts. Without this hormone, their growth and physical development can be affected. To support healthy growth, these children require growth hormone replacement therapy, which usually involves regular injections. Instead of using traditional needles—which can be painful and frightening for children—the Cool Click device delivers the hormone through a needle-free system. This makes the treatment process more comfortable, safer, and less stressful.

The device includes adjustable dosing features, allowing doctors and caregivers to deliver the exact amount of Saizen needed for each child. This is very important because the required dose may vary depending on the child's age, weight, and specific medical condition. Another unique feature of the Cool Click is its bright and colorful design. It was intentionally created to look friendly and non-threatening, so children feel less anxious when receiving their treatment.

Madajet

The Madajet injector is a needle-free device commonly used in dentistry to deliver local anesthesia. It works using pneumatic pressure (compressed air or gas), which pushes the anesthetic into the skin without a needle. When used, the device releases the drug as a fine, high-pressure stream that penetrates about 4 to 5.5 mm beneath the skin surface. This creates a small raised bump, called a wheal, usually 5–6 mm wide, showing that the anesthetic has been delivered correctly. Each injection delivers a precise dose of 0.1 cc, making it accurate for numbing small areas needed for dental treatments. Since it avoids needles, the Madajet reduces patient fear, lowers the risk of needle injuries, and provides a quicker, less painful experience.

Intraject

The Intraject system is a modern medical device created to give medicines without using a needle. It works by producing a very fine, high-pressure stream of liquid that passes through the skin and delivers the medicine directly into the body. This makes the process quick, clean, and much less scary for patients who are afraid of needles. Since it comes pre-filled with medicine and is meant for one-time use, there is no need to reload or reuse it. This not only makes it convenient but also reduces the chances of infection or contamination. Another big advantage is that the device is easy to handle. With just a little training, a doctor, nurse, patient, or even a family member can use it safely. It also helps in giving injections at home without needing to visit a hospital every time.

Finally, the Intraject system provides a virtually pain-free experience, which makes it especially useful for children, people with needle phobia, and patients who need frequent injections.

Vitajet 3

The Vitajet 3 is a user-friendly and cost-effective needle-free system for insulin delivery. It doesn't require maintenance or reassembly. The device uses disposable nozzles that are replaced weekly, combining the quality of a reusable medical device with the safety and convenience of a sterile single-use part. Its clear, easy-to-read Crystal Check nozzle lets users see the correct dose before injection and confirm that all insulin has been delivered. Approved by the FDA in 1996 for subcutaneous insulin injections, the Vitajet 3 has safely and efficiently delivered hundreds of thousands of injections without using needles. . (Theintz & Sizonenko, 1991), (Munsh, Hegde, & Bashir, 2001), (de Wit, Engwerda, Tack, & de Galan, 2015), (Bora V.G., 2023).

Injex needle-free injections for infiltration anaesthesia

INJEX is a needle-free injection system used in dentistry. Instead of using a needle and syringe, it pushes the anesthetic (numbing medicine) into the gum through a very tiny hole (only 0.18 mm wide). The medicine enters the tissues under pressure, so the patient feels little to no pain. The dentist places the ampoule (small medicine container) on the gum. It is kept at a 90° angle directly above the tooth that needs treatment. When the system is activated, the anesthetic is delivered quickly and exactly where it is needed.

Pediatric patients

Children are often scared of dental treatment and especially of needles. INJEX is very helpful because it does not use a needle, so kids feel less afraid. Dentists can easily numb baby teeth (deciduous teeth) with this system. Only a small dose (0.3 ml) is needed, which works quickly and reduces stress for the child.

Use in adult

For Maxillary

For Mandibular

Many adults are also afraid of injections and the pain of dental treatment. INJEX removes the need for needles, so the process feels almost painless. This makes dental care more comfortable and less stressful for patients. (Vishwanathaiah S, 2024), (Nikolaos N. Dabarakis, 2007nov-dec), (Alameeri A.A.)

MARKETED PRODUCT OF NFI SYSTEM :

(Mohizin, 2018), (Al-Kaf & Othman, 2017), (al.)s, 2012).

Product names	company	Type of system	Actuation mechanism	Department of penetration	Drug types	Drug volumes
Medi-jector vision	Antares Pharma Inc.	Liquid based NFI	Spring	Subcutaneous	Insulin	-
Biojector 2000	Bioject	Liquid based NFI	Compressed gas	Subcutaneous Intramuscular	liquid	1
Vitajet3	Bioject	Liquid based NFI	Spring	Subcutaneous	Insulin	0.02-0.5
Iject	Bioject	Liquid based NFI	Compressed gas	Intramuscular Subcutaneous intra dermal	liquid	variable
Intraject	Weston medical	Liquid based NFI	Compressed gas	Subcutaneous	liquid	0.5
Penjet	Penjet corporation	Liquid based NFI	Compressed gas	Intramuscular Subcutaneous intra dermal	liquid	0.1-0.5
Injex150	Injex	Liquid based NFI	Spring	Subcutaneous	insulin	0.8-1.5
Crossject	Crossject	Liquid based NFI	Spring	Intramuscular Subcutaneous intra dermal	liquid	0.2-1
Depixel Depo injection	Lundbeck	Depot based NFI	Compressed gas	Intramuscular	liquid	2-3
Powderject system	Powderject pharmaceuticals	Powder based NFI	Compressed gas	Intra dermal	powder	-

APPLICATIONS: (Raghuvanshi RS, 2011), (Patel P, 2016)

- **Clinical trials:** for needle-free injection technologies are carried out in a similar way to trials for traditional needles. However, they mainly check how safe, effective, and comfortable these devices are for patients. The trials look at things like wound healing, pain levels, immune response, and correct drug delivery. Researchers compare needle-free devices with normal needle-and-syringe methods to see if they work as well or better—for example, in producing antibodies for vaccines or giving insulin to people with diabetes.

- **Vaccinations:** It can be used for large-scale vaccination efforts and for new types of DNA vaccines. This method often works better because it delivers the vaccine directly to immune cells in the skin.
- **Diabetes:** NFIT is a good way to give insulin, potentially working faster than regular shots and making it easier for people who need to take insulin often.
- **Skin Treatments:** It's effective for treating scars, wrinkles, and warts by delivering medications like Botox or other skin treatments.
- **Pain Relief:** NFIT can be used to deliver local anaesthetics, like lidocaine, to numb the skin for small medical procedures or before getting an IV.
- **Hormone Therapy:** It's also used to deliver hormones and proteins, such as human growth hormones.

THE FUTURE SCOPE

The future of needle-free injection systems looks very bright, thanks to new technology and the need for safer, less painful ways to deliver medicines. Still, challenges like high costs and limited compatibility with some drugs must be solved before these systems can be used everywhere.

Technological progress: Companies are creating devices that are more accurate, easy to use, and effective.

New features include

- Smart technology with mobile apps for monitoring doses and patient use.
- Better control over how deep and how much medicine is injected.
- Wearable injectors that allow continuous monitoring.

Wider applications: These systems are now being used not just for insulin and vaccines, but also in Cancer treatment (oncology), Pain management, Skin treatments (cosmetic and medical), Fertility care, Paediatrics and elderly care, where avoiding pain is especially important

Rising self-use: As chronic diseases increase and more people prefer home care, needle-free systems allow patients to inject themselves safely, reducing hospital visits and saving money.

Expansion in developing countries: With higher healthcare spending, more awareness, and rising incomes, these markets are expected to grow quickly.

Biologics growth: The biopharma industry's demand for advanced delivery methods is driving innovation in needle-free systems.

➤ **Opportunities and scope**

Mass vaccination: Useful for large-scale immunization drives because they are faster, reduce logistics issues, and help people afraid of needles. Supported by WHO and global health groups.

Better patient compliance: By reducing pain and fear, patients are more likely to follow long-term treatments, such as for diabetes.

Higher safety: They lower the risk of accidental needle injuries and blood borne infections.

No sharp waste: Eliminates costs and environmental problems from disposing of used needles.

Targeted delivery: Devices like microneedle patches can deliver medicine more precisely, often needing smaller doses and improving effectiveness. (Gupta J, 2011) (Kwon SY, 2010) (: Sarasin Khotthada, 2024), (Daichi Igarashi, 2024).

CONCLUSION

Development of drug delivery systems that can penetrate the skin has largely relied on basic engineering principles. Traditional syringes with hypodermic needles often cause pain, trigger needle phobia, and sometimes lead to accidental needle-stick injuries, all of which can reduce patient compliance and create additional problems. Needle-free technology offers a solution by delivering a wide range of medications into the body with the same effectiveness as conventional syringes, but without causing unnecessary pain. These devices are simple to use, do not require expert supervision, and are easy to store and dispose of safely. They are suitable for delivering drugs to sensitive areas, such as the cornea, and can efficiently administer intramuscular, subcutaneous, and intradermal injections.

Needle-free systems work by using a power source either mechanical or force-based to push the drug through a very fine nozzle at speeds close to the speed of sound.

Many companies have invested in this technology, and several FDA-approved needle-free devices are already available in the market.

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